

Turnbull's blue when freshly prepared has been suggested to be due to an excess of ferrous molecules where the ferrous iron is not saturated with regard to its maximum valency.

I wish to thank Dr. N. R. Dhar of the Allahabad University for his kind interest and helpful suggestions in connection with the work. Thanks are due to Dr. R. Samuel of the Aligarh University for kindly allowing me to work in the Physics Laboratory there and for the guidance that he and his Assistant Dr. R. K. Asundi, whose help I gratefully acknowledge, have given me while taking the absorption photographs of the solutions. I thank my friend Mr. N. Ghatak for his kindly helping me to take a few photographs with constant deviation spectrograph at the chemistry laboratory of Allahabad University.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
BAREILLY COLLEGE,
BAREILLY.

Received September 8, 1934.

Photochemical Reaction between Iodine and Oxalate.

BY N. R. DHAR, A. K. BHATTACHARYA AND B. L. MUKERJI.

Amongst the photochemical reactions taking place in solutions, the iodine-oxalate reaction is one which has been investigated by several chemists. Since 1916, when one of the authors (Dhar, *Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amstardam*, 1916, **16**, 1097; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 707; 1923, **123**, 1856; *Anal. Chim.*, 1919, **9**, 130) showed that this reaction is highly sensitive to light and that the dark reaction is slow and has a very high temperature coefficient, a great deal of work has been carried on this chemical change. Unfortunately, there is disagreement in the results obtained by different workers (Berthoud and Bellenot, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, **7**, 307;

Berthoud, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, 27, 527; *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, 16, 393; Briers, Chapman and Walters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 562; Mukherji and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1306; Bhattacharya and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1929, 6, 451, 473; 1930, 7, 677; Dhar, Bhattacharya and Mukherji, *Nature*, 1933, 131, 840; Young and Style, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, 27, 493; Allmand and Young, *ibid.*, p. 515; Griffith and McKeown, *ibid.*, 1932, 28, 107, 752).

Dhar showed that the addition of an iodide markedly retards this as well as several other reactions involving iodine. Most of the researches on the kinetics of this reaction have been carried on with aqueous solutions of iodine dissolved in potassium iodide and hence the observed velocities have been greatly decreased by the presence of potassium iodide. In order to avoid the retarding influence of potassium iodide, we have carried on experiments with aqueous solutions of iodine without any potassium iodide and the results are recorded in this communication, which also contains an important relation between light absorption and chemical reactivity.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Merck's pure iodine was carefully sublimed for further purification. The potassium oxalate used was Merck's guaranteed reagent purified by recrystallisation from solutions in conductivity water. All solutions were prepared in conductivity water.

For the ultraviolet light source a Hanau quartz-mercury vapour lamp and for the infra-red, an 8000 watt gas-filled tungsten filament lamp were used. The solution filters used for the ultraviolet light have already been described (Bhattacharya, Prakash and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 209, 139). For isolating radiations of wavelengths $8500\text{\AA}$, a saturated solution of potassium dichromate in a cobalt glass cell of 1 cm. thickness and for $8750\text{\AA}$, the same solution in a cobalt glass cell and $N/7000$ -neocyanine in a 1 cm. thick glass cell were used. The reaction vessel was a quartz 3 cm. cube cell. For measurements of the energy absorbed a Moll thermopile with a sensitive galvanometer was used. The velocity of the reaction was followed by estimating the unchanged iodine against dilute solutions of sodium thiosulphate. The following experimental results have been obtained.

TABLE I.

N-K₂C₂O₄ and *N*/850-I₂, 20 c.c. of each solution mixed.

Condition.	Temp.	K ₁ (semimolecular) after deducting the dark reaction.	Temp. Coeff.	Quantum yield.	
Dark	15°	Unimol. K ₁ {	4·64 (1 + 3)	—	
	20				0·000310 (1)
	25				0·000677 (2)
	30				0·00144 (3)
	40				0·00285 (4)
			4·07 (4 + 5)	—	
3536Å (corning glass)	15	0·0153	2·44	98	
	20	0·0253		216	
	25	0·0374		342	
3125Å	15	0·00168	2·38	—	
	20	0·0270			
	25	0·0400			
3452Å	15	0·0168	2·38	83	
	20	0·0270		228	
	25	0·040		367	
3512Å	15	0·0234	2·25	88	
	20	0·0352		135	
	25	0·0527		220	
3340Å	15	0·0275	2·02	106	
	20	0·0403		164	
	25	0·0555		242	
8500Å	20	0·00413	3·54	1·05	
	25	0·00820		5·4	
	30	0·0146		9·7	
	40	0·0491			
8750Å	15	0·00149	3·92	—	
	20	0·00285			
	25	0·00560			

It has been shown in a previous publication (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **35**, 2389) that a light filter consisting of K₂CrO₄ (0·03 g. in 100 c.c.) and CoCl₂ (saturated solution, 3·66*M*) each in a quartz cell of 1 cm. thickness transmits radiations of mean wave-lengths 3125Å. Similarly 2·08*M*-nickel nitrate and 3·66*M*-CoCl₂ transmit 3452Å, 0·00154*M*-K₂Cr₂O₇ and 3·66*M*-CoCl₂ transmit 3512Å and 3·66*M*-CoCl₂ transmits 3340Å.

For obtaining radiations of mean wave-length 3536Å, a corning glass filter was used. The amount of light transmission by this filter

is much less than that of the solution filters and hence the velocity of the reaction is less than with other filters.

In this as well as in many exothermal photochemical reactions, the quantum yield is much greater than unity and increases markedly with the increase of temperature and the acceleration of the reaction by light absorption. It appears that the energy given out by the reaction is utilised in the activation of further molecules of the reacting substances and hence the quantum yield is greater than unity. In these exothermal photochemical reactions, the activation of the reacting molecules or their atomisation and the loosening of the binding forces of the molecules are produced by the absorbed light and the energy liberated in the chemical changes.

Relation between the Velocity of the Reaction and the Intensity of the Incident Radiation (or Absorbed Energy).

The majority of workers believe that the velocity of this reaction in light is not directly proportional to the intensity of the incident radiations but varies as the square root of the intensity of incident radiation, although A. K. Bhattacharya and N. R. Dhar have observed that by using an aqueous solution of iodine and in radiations of mean wave-lengths $5650\text{\AA}$, and $7304\text{\AA}$, the relation between the velocity and the light intensity approaches unity. The following results show that the relation between the velocity and incident light intensity in the reaction between $N\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and $N/850\text{-I}_2$ at 20° in absence of potassium iodide can vary from $1/3$ to $5/4$.

TABLE II.

Wave-length	...	3512 $\text{\AA}$	3340 $\text{\AA}$	3536 $\text{\AA}$ (corning glass)	8500 $\text{\AA}$	8750 $\text{\AA}$
Observed ratio of velocities		1.32	1.79	3.25	3.97	2.71
Ratio of incident light intensity		4	4	6.25	4.34	2.44

The results recorded in Tables I and II show that when the photochemical reaction between potassium oxalate and aqueous iodine is highly accelerated by ultraviolet radiations, the velocity varies as $I^{1/2}$ except in the case of the corning glass filter, which transmits less than the solution filters, whilst in presence of infra-red radiations of wave-lengths $8750\text{\AA}$, which accelerate the reaction much less than ultraviolet light, the reaction velocity is proportional to $I^{5/4}$. With the

corning glass filter, the acceleration of the reaction was less than with the solution filters and the velocity is nearly proportional to $I^{\frac{1}{2}}$ with the corning glass. We have observed that the amount of light absorbed by the reacting mixture is directly proportional to the intensity of the incident radiation. Hence the reaction between potassium oxalate and aqueous iodine is not always proportional to the square root of the light intensity, as assumed by Berthoud and Bellenot, Briers, Chapman and Walters, and Allmand and Young (*loc. cit.*), but can vary as $I^{\frac{1}{2}}$ to $I^{\frac{3}{2}}$ depending on the acceleration of the reaction in presence of light. This is certainly one of the many reactions which have been proved by us (Bhattacharya and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 473; Dhar and Bhagwat, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 190, 415; *ibid.*, 1931, 199, 406) to show a variable relation between the velocity and the light intensity or the amount of energy absorbed.

Temperature Coefficients.

From the results recorded in Table I, it will be seen that the temperature coefficient of the dark reaction velocity has the value 4.64 between 15° and 25° and 4.21 between 20° and 30°. The temperature coefficient in ultraviolet light, which markedly accelerates the reaction, varies from 2.02 to 2.44 between 15° and 25°. Moreover, it will be observed that the greater the velocity of the reaction in light, the smaller is the temperature coefficient of the reaction.

When the reaction is accelerated by infra-red radiations of wave-lengths 8500Å and 8750Å, which affect the velocity much less than ultraviolet, the difference between the temperature coefficients of the thermal and photochemical velocities is much less. In radiations of wave-lengths 8500Å, the temperature coefficient between 20° and 30° has the value 3.54 and in radiations of wave-lengths 8750Å, the value between 15° and 25° is 3.92. Hence we can conclude that the greater the acceleration of the reaction due to light absorption, the smaller is the temperature coefficient of the velocity or of quantum yield.

It has already been reported that iodide ions markedly retard this reaction. We have carried on some experiments on the dark reaction in presence of KI, because recently Berthoud reported that he could not reproduce our previous results nor the results obtained by himself

and Bellenot. We have obtained the following results in the dark with $N\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and $N/850\text{-I}_2$ containing $N/277\text{-KI}$; 20 c.c. of each solution were used.

TABLE III.

Temp.	K_1 (unimolecular).	Temp- Coeff.
22°	0.0000508	—
32°	0.000449	8.84
42°	0.00325	7.20

The Arrhenius A for this reaction has the very high value 18800. It will be interesting to note that the Arrhenius A for the velocity of the decomposition of an aqueous solution of trichloroacetic acid in the dark has also the high value 18610. Using $1.5N\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, $0.0088N\text{-I}_2$ and $0.034N\text{-KI}$, Dhar obtained 7.2 as the value of the temperature coefficient for a 10° rise between 25° and 40° and the Arrhenius $A=18355$. In the earlier experiments of Dhar, the amounts of the reacting substances were such as to make the velocity of the reaction in the dark a little higher than those recorded above. Hence the Arrhenius A is slightly smaller than the present value. The foregoing results show that when the reaction velocity is greatly retarded due to KI, the temperature coefficient of the dark reaction, which has the value 4.64 between 15° and 25° (Arrhenius $A=13160$) in absence of KI, markedly increases and the results are entirely reproducible. It has been repeatedly observed in these laboratories that retardation of a reaction by a negative catalyst generally causes an increase in the temperature coefficient of the velocity of a reaction.

On applying the Perrin-Lewis radiation hypothesis, we get $8600\text{\AA}$ as the maximum wave-length capable of accelerating the reaction in presence of KI and $10500\text{\AA}$ for the reaction in the absence of potassium iodide. Actually we have been able to accelerate the reaction in absence of KI by radiations of wave-lengths $8500\text{\AA}$ and $8750\text{\AA}$ and the reaction in presence of KI by radiations of $\lambda=8500\text{\AA}$.

Influence of Stirring on the Kinetics of the Reaction.

Attempts have been made from time to time to determine whether the velocity of a homogeneous photochemical reaction is affected by shaking or stirring the reacting substances. Recently Young and Style (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the temperature coefficient of the

photochemical reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine in presence of KI markedly decreases when the mixture is well stirred. From the laws of light absorption, Bhagwat and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 535) have deduced a relation, which shows that when the relation between the light absorption and the velocity of the reaction deviates markedly from unity, stirring will lead to increased velocity and decreased temperature coefficient. As this is an interesting point, we have carried on some measurements on the influence of stirring on this reaction. The reacting substances were placed in the same reaction vessel as before and stirred by a stout glass rod driven by a small motor. The amount of light falling on the mixture in these experiments is less than in the previous experiments as the light was allowed to pass through an aperture of a diaphragm with a diameter 2.5 cm. The results are as follows with 10 c. c. of *N*-K₂C₂O₄ and 10 c.c. of *N*/850-aqueous iodine without KI.

TABLE IV.

Wave-length.	Temp.	$K_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (semimolecular) after deducting the dark reaction.	Temp. Coeff.
8500Å.	Stirred	20°	1.62
		30	
	Unstir- red	20	3.5
		30	
3340Å	Stirred	20	1.42
		30	
	Unstir- red	20	2.02
		30	
3536Å (corning glass)	Stirred	20	1.51
		30	
	Unstir- red	20	2.40
		30	

The foregoing results show that on stirring, the velocities of the reaction in radiations of wave-lengths 3340, 3536 and 8500Å are greatly increased and the temperature coefficients are considerably

lowered. Moreover, the temperature coefficients in the stirred reaction mixtures show much less variation in radiations of different wave-lengths than in the unstirred condition.

In this reaction, the light absorption is high and the reaction is markedly accelerated by stirring. When the light absorption is feeble, stirring is not likely to influence the velocity.

It has already been reported that in radiations of wave-lengths 8500Å when the light intensity is varied, the observed ratio of velocities has the value 3.97 when the ratio of the light intensity is 4.34. We have investigated the influence of stirring on the relations between the velocity and the light intensity in radiation of wave-lengths 8500Å and the experimental results at 20° are recorded below.

TABLE V.

$N\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and $N/850$ -iodine (10 c.c. each).

Diameter of the aperture.	$K_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (semimolecular) after deducting the dark reaction.	Ratio of velocities.	Ratio of light intensity.
2.5 cm.	0.0459 (I)	$\frac{\text{I}}{\text{II}} = 1.51$	4.34
1.2	0.0303 (II)	$\frac{\text{II}}{\text{III}} = 1.09$	1.40
1.0	0.0277 (III)	$\frac{\text{I}}{\text{III}} = 1.66$	6.25

These results show that when the solution is stirred, the velocity of the reaction between potassium oxalate and aqueous iodine in radiations of wave-lengths 8500Å is greatly increased and it becomes nearly proportional to $I^{\frac{1}{2}}$, whilst with the unstirred solution the reaction is nearly directly proportional to the light intensity in radiations of wave-lengths 8500Å. It is of interest to note that in the dark reaction in presence of an excess of potassium oxalate, the rate of disappearance of iodine follows the unimolecular formula but in presence of ultraviolet, visible or infra-red radiations, the velocity of the disappearance of iodine, is semimolecular. This behaviour is also observed with some other photochemical reactions involving iodine, *e.g.*, sodium formate and iodine; sodium citrate and iodine; sodium malate and iodine; ferrous sulphate and iodine; and sodium nitrite and iodine.

It is difficult to state whether this behaviour is an absorption effect only or due to the formation of atomic iodine on illumination.

Chemical Reactivity and Light Absorption.

From the researches of Pringsheim and Rosen (*Z. Physik*, 1928, 50, 1) we know that there are four absorption spectra of iodine; the well known red-green absorption, two absorption spectra in the ultraviolet below $\lambda=2000\text{\AA}$ and a very faint one in the infra-red ($>8000\text{\AA}$). This latter is likely to belong to a metastable level. The acceleration of the iodine-oxalate reaction in radiations $\lambda=8500\text{\AA}$ and $8750\text{\AA}$ as actually observed may be due to this metastable level.

We have carefully measured the extinction coefficients of a mixture of $N\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and $N/850$ -aqueous iodine by a Nutting's spectrophotometer and the results are given below.

TABLE VI.

Wave-length ($\text{\AA}$)	...	7000	6707	5970	5670	5490	5320	5200	5000
Extinction coeff.	...	0.03	0.06	0.10	0.14	0.18	0.20	0.24	0.28
Wave-length ($\text{\AA}$)	...	4910	4800	4720	4670	4550	4400		
Extinction coeff.	...	0.32	0.36	0.41	0.46	0.51	0.60		

These results show that all radiations between 7000 to $4400\text{\AA}$ are absorbed by aqueous iodine.

From the results recorded in the foregoing pages, it will be seen that the iodine-oxalate reaction is markedly accelerated by infra-red radiations of wave-lengths $8500\text{\AA}$ and $8750\text{\AA}$. The limits of sensitised decomposition and photochemical decomposition with iodine molecules are $8050\text{\AA}$ and $4995\text{\AA}$ respectively. It appears, therefore, that the presence of oxalate markedly sensitises the decomposition of iodine molecules, which become reactive in radiations of longer wave-lengths on the addition of oxalate. Using a copper arc we have carefully photographed the absorption spectra of $N/1700$ -aqueous iodine and $N/2$ -potassium oxalate separately and a mixture containing 10 c.c. of $N\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and 10 c.c. of $N/850$ -aqueous iodine and we find that the iodine solution alone shows almost complete absorption in the ultraviolet from $2700\text{\AA}$, whilst with the oxalate solution, almost complete absorption in the ultraviolet begins from $3000\text{\AA}$. In the case of the mixture of the iodine and oxalate, almost complete absorption in the ultraviolet starts nearly from $3826\text{\AA}$. These results showing that the absorption of light by a solution of an oxalate is appreciably increased by the addition of a dilute iodine solution, are of great interest from the view point of the nature of chemical reactivity. In other words,

the sensitisation of an oxalate solution by iodine is associated with marked increase of light absorption in the ultraviolet.

In the reaction between oxalate-iodine, the chemical change involved appears to be

Similar is the case with the other halogens with oxalic acid or an oxalate. That oxalate ion is taking part in these reactions is evident from the fact that the velocity of reaction is greater with an oxalate than oxalic acid. The first stage in these reactions appears to be the formation of an additive compound of the halogen molecule and the reducing agent having greater light absorption capacity and not the atomisation of the halogen molecules as has been hitherto supposed.

SUMMARY.

1. The reaction between an excess of potassium oxalate and aqueous iodine in absence of KI is unimolecular in the dark and semi-molecular in light.

2. The temperature coefficient of the reaction velocity between 15° and 25° has the values 4.64 (dark), 3.92 (8750Å), 3.54 (8500Å), 2.44 (corning glass 3536Å), 2.38 (3452Å), 2.38 (3125Å), 2.25 (3512Å), 2.03 (3340Å). The greater the acceleration due to light, the smaller is the temperature coefficient. The velocity of the reaction is greatly retarded by KI and in its presence ($N/277$), the temperature coefficient between 22° and 32° in the dark has the value 8.84.

3. The relation between the velocity and the incident light intensity or the absorbed energy is not constant but varies from 1/3 to 5/4. When the reaction is much accelerated by light the relation becomes small and when the acceleration due to light is comparatively small, the relation has a higher value.

4. When the reaction mixture is stirred, the reaction velocity in light is markedly accelerated and the temperature coefficient is lowered.

5. Almost complete absorption of light in the ultraviolet by a normal solution of an oxalate begins from 3000Å, by a $N/850$ solution of iodine from 2700Å, whilst with the mixture of oxalate and iodine almost complete light absorption begins from 3826Å. Hence the absorption of light by a solution of an oxalate is appreciably increased by the addition of iodine.